

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Babakhonov Jafar Mukhiddinovich

**METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF TAXES ON THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC
ACTIVITIES OF THE ENTERPRISE**

**NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI**

2023/IYUL

